

On the Nature of Hydrolytic Adsorption with reference to the Adsorption of Electrolytes and of Water.

Part I

General and Theoretical Introduction

BY

JNANENDRA NATH MUKHERJEE.

The nature of what is usually called "hydrolytic adsorption" has of late years attracted a good deal of attention. In a paper 'On the Adsorption of Ions' (Mukherjee, *Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44 [VI], 330,) it was suggested that surfaces adsorbing neutral water molecules can react with acids and alkalis in solution. In another place (*loc. cit.*, p. 340-45) it was stated in connection with the origin of the latent acidity of sour soil that "the gel adsorbs anions by chemical affinity. The anions may be—

- (1) of organic acids, such as humus acid ;
- (2) of simple electrolytes like chlorides, sulphates, carbonates, etc.
- (3) hydroxyl ions from water.

Owing to the complex chemical nature of the gel and the enormous specific surface of the gels large quantities of anions may be adsorbed. An equivalent number of cations remain near the surface as the mobile second sheet or as electrically adsorbed. The exchange of bases is

simply due to the displacement of these ions, when the displacement is quantitative, equivalent amounts are exchanged. The anions primarily adsorbed or the cations in the second sheet are not of one kind. The relative numbers and chemical natures of these ions will evidently vary with different soils. An extract with a neutral salt can only be acid when the cations displaced from the second sheet (or electrically adsorbed) contain hydrogen ions or such ions as aluminium, which hydrolyse in dilute aqueous solutions. * * * That sometimes considerable quantities of bases are exchanged should be referred to the enormous surface of these gels and that probably the surface is saturated with anions. As crystalloids (insoluble) are also present, the type of exchange considered by Paneth (*loc. cit.*) is also possible. It is needless to point out that in the discussion only the theoretically simple case has been considered. Complications due to simultaneous primary adsorption and their mutual displacement are not always negligible. Besides the changes may not be restricted to the surface, formation of solid solutions, etc., are not excluded. Considering all these complex influences, it is interesting to note that most of the observed regularities correspond to the theoretically simple case."

The nature of the exchange of bases was also explained from the point of view of the exchange of adsorbed ions with those in solution.

In the present paper the theoretical considerations have been further elaborated and a brief summary has been given of the experimental evidence obtained in this laboratory during the last 4 years in support of the theory. The experimental portion together with a discussion of alternative explanations will be published in a series of papers dealing with individual systems.

General Remarks.

We shall apply the term 'hydrolytic' adsorption' to cases where acids or alkalis are liberated by the interaction between solutions of salts having a neutral reaction and insoluble substances which do not give an acid or alkaline extract with water. We would also restrict the use of this term *to cases where a simple chemical reaction between stoichiometric quantities cannot account for the facts*, or in other words, the facts do not warrant a representation in terms of reactions between molecules with definite molecular weights.

It is apparent that if the reaction of the solution of the neutral salt after contact with the insoluble phase becomes acid, a corresponding quantity of base must separate and remain associated with the insoluble phase. Also it is scarcely necessary to mention that such a splitting up of a salt into an acid and a base involves either of three possibilities, namely,

- (1) an interaction between the salt and water molecules (primarily) adsorbed on the surface, or,
- (2) the direct or indirect replacement of hydrogen ions present in the surface layer by a cation present in the solution, or,
- (3) the direct or indirect replacement of hydroxyl ions in the surface layer by anions in solution.

In order to explain the nature of hydrolytic adsorption it is not sufficient to say that 'hydrolytic' separation of the constituents of the salt has taken place as a result of adsorption. It is merely a statement of what has happened, unless we can define the nature of the adsorption process and can give a more or less definite picture of the changes in the surface layer. From the point of view adopted in this and previous papers (*Phil. Mag.*, *loc. cit.*;

Far. Soc. Disc., Oct., 1920; Published as *The Physics and Chemistry of Colloids*, *Apl.*, 1921; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 476; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173,) it is possible to imagine several types of reactions which will lead to the liberation of acids or alkalis when a neutral (salt) solution is brought in contact with an insoluble phase.

We have formulated them under the heads A, B, C and D. The experimental evidence in support of each type is briefly stated under each head.

A. Interaction between a Neutral Electrolyte and Adsorbed Acids of which the Anion is Primarily Adsorbed by the Adsorbent.

(1)

As a special case of this type of reaction let us assume that the adsorbent is an insoluble salt BA where the base BOH and the acid HA are both strongly ionised in their solutions. Suppose now that the insoluble salt BA under certain conditions of precipitation develop a large amount of specific surface * and that it can also adsorb a considerable quantity of the acid HA'. The extent of adsorption will evidently depend on the nature of the adsorbent and on that of the acid as also on the concentration of the acid.

Let us now further suppose that the adsorbent does not adsorb the molecules of the acid as such but that the anions A' are 'primarily adsorbed' on the surface in virtue of the chemical affinity of the atoms on the surface in the sense in which the term has been used by the writer in previous papers.

The system composed of the adsorbent BA and the adsorbed acid HA' will have from our point of view the following characteristic properties :—

* The amount adsorbed per unit surface, we have reasons to think, also varies with the conditions of preparation.

(i) If the adsorption of anions be very intense it will be difficult to wash out the last trace of the adsorbed acid and in suitable cases it will be possible to show that the substance retains adsorbed acid even after repeated washings with pure water.

Usually, however, on long continued washing the adsorbed substance will come out continuously till it is completely removed.

(ii) The adsorption of the anion will impart a negative charge to the surface. This will not be the case if neutral molecules as such are adsorbed on the surface or if the constituent ions of the electrolyte remain in the 'primarily' adsorbed layer.

The increase in negative charge will, when the adsorption of the cation is not very prominent, be noticeable at low electrolyte concentrations. At higher concentrations the 'electrical adsorption' of the cation will predominate and a lowering of the negative charge will be observed.

(iii) It might also be pointed out in this connection that the amount so adsorbed is usually small because the primarily adsorbed layer is formed through what might be called a sort of chemical combination and is determined by the number of places on the surface where adsorbed molecules can be 'fixed' up. *The adsorbent has thus a 'saturation capacity' determined by the number of such places per unit surface.* For a given sample of an adsorbent prepared under identical conditions a definite amount of an anion will be necessary to saturate unit surface.

(iv) *If only the anions A' are primarily absorbed,* equal amounts of different electrolytes containing the same anion but different cations will be adsorbed, when the effective anion concentration (or rather activity) remains the same. Moreover, this condition will be satisfied only when the surface exerts no chemical affinity on the cations.

(v) Since the forces acting between the charged surface and the cations in the mobile layer are mainly electrical in nature the freely moving hydrogen ions will be easily replaceable by other cations of neutral salts. The amount of acids liberated by neutral salts will depend on the amount of replaceable hydrogen ions (which in its turn is determined by the amount of anions remaining primarily adsorbed), on the concentration (or activity) of the cation of the salt, and on the relative (electrical and chemical) adsorbability and mobility of the cation.

Here also we have assumed that the anion of the salt which has been added is not adsorbable by the surface—an assumption which is not true in all cases.

(vi) It is evident that the system is acting like an acid in the sense that it has got replaceable hydrogen ions. *The essential difference from the ordinary conception of an acid is that the adsorbent need not at all be 'acidic' or 'basic' in character and that the 'acidity' may be due to the adsorption of acid, resulting from the primary adsorption of anions. Consequently there is no definite and simple stoichiometric relationship between the amount of the adsorbent and the amount of replaceable hydrogen ions, and as stated before, the ratio of the amounts of replaceable hydrogen ions to the mass of the adsorbent depends on the mode of preparation and on the adsorbability of the anion.*

Moreover, the quantitative relationships between the concentrations of interacting ions are governed by the considerations set forth in this and previous papers and not by the usual conceptions applicable to the case of molecularly dissolved acids.

(vii) The system BA with adsorbed acids, on treatment with the solution of a neutral salt, will evidently be converted into a system containing adsorbed salts. The reaction may be represented as follows *assuming that all*

the hydrogen or potassium ions are in the mobile sheet of the double layer :

(viii) Depending on the relative adsorbabilities and concentrations of potassium and hydrogen ions the substance II may be partially converted into the substances I when brought in contact with pure water liberating the corresponding alkali as represented below :—

The above reaction is the counterpart of the usual type of hydrolysis.

The total amount of alkali so liberated will depend on the amount of potassium in II, on the relative adsorbabilities of hydrogen and potassium ions and on the concentration of hydrogen ions. The concentration of the liberated alkali will depend on the ratio of the two ions in the double layer.

(2) Other Adsorbents.

The general case where the adsorbent need not be polar in character does not need further comment except

* The surface is usually hydrated, the quantity of water hydrating the surface is represented by y grammoles per x grammoles of the solid adsorbent—the gram molecular wt. of the adsorbent may be taken to be that corresponding to the simple chemical formula for the purpose of representing the quantities involved. The solid substances I and II are not totally different in the sense that only the composition and the double layer changes. On the addition of the solution of potassium chloride some of the hydrogen ions in the double layer are replaced by an equivalent number of potassium ions.

that, as we shall see presently, the 'acidic' or 'basic' character of an adsorbent will determine the nature of the anion which will be 'primarily' adsorbed. An adsorbent which will show a marked capacity to adsorb primarily hydroxyl ions, or, in other words, to react with hydroxyl ions in virtue of the chemical character of the atoms on the surface, will evidently be 'acidic' in character. A 'basic' adsorbent will show a marked capacity to adsorb primarily, that is, to react with hydrogen ions. Now these are the constituent ions of water and as it is well-known from the effect of even very low concentrations of electrolytes on electro-osmosis, cataphoresis and allied phenomena that hydrogen and hydroxyl ions are likely to be adsorbed from water in appreciable quantities in suitable cases. For the sake of convenience the adsorption of hydroxyl ions (a special case of anion adsorption) and of hydrogen ions (a special case of cation adsorption) will be dealt with in a separate section.

B. Interaction between a Neutral Electrolyte and adsorbed Alkali of which the Cation is Primarily Adsorbed by the Adsorbent.

This case also does not require any detailed consideration as the criteria enumerated above are all equally applicable with the difference that the adsorption of a cation will increase the positive charge of the surface and that the mobile sheet will consist of anions (hydroxyl ions in the case of alkalis). It may be pointed out here that the alkali metal ions do not seem to be 'primarily' adsorbable (Mukherjee and Roy, *J. Chem. Soc., loc. cit.*) The replacement of hydroxyl ions by other anions will be more complicated as chemical affinity between the surface and the replacing anions has to be taken into account.

Experimental Evidence in support of Reactions Formulated under A and B.

It is well-known that polar precipitates adsorb electrolytes. Recently Weiser and Sherrich (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1919, 23, 205,) have found that precipitates of barium sulphate strongly adsorb electrolytes. For this reason this precipitate was first chosen for our experiments. A summary of the main results obtained in collaboration with Mr. J. K. Basu is given below.

Experiments with Barium Sulphate.

Weiser and others have shown that marked adsorption occurs when the medium in which the insoluble salt is precipitated contains the electrolytes. We have also found this to be the case. Precipitations of barium sulphate were carried on in presence of the following acids:—hydrochloric, acetic, phosphoric, citric, tartaric and sulphuric. The precipitate was washed repeatedly with pure water having a p_H between 6.4 to 6.6 at 28°, till the washed water is free from acid as shown by a p_H value between 6.2 to 6.4. Two equal portions of the precipitate are then left in contact with saturated potassium chloride and water respectively for 24 hours. There were no extraneous sources of acids and alkalis in these experiments.

(1) After contact with the neutral salt a marked acid reaction ranging up to a p_H value of 2.2 and mostly lower than 4.6 is observed in the potassium chloride solution. The water of the parallel experiment does not show (when the proper care in washing has been taken) a p_H value lower than 5.8. If the potassium chloride solution is replaced by a fresh volume of the solution, acid is again liberated but the p_H of successive extracts increases in value and is to be referred to a decrease in the ratio of hydrogen to potassium ions in the double layer.

The samples used always liberate small quantities of acids in contact with water. This explains why, on treatment with potassium chloride solution, traces of adsorbed anions are also liberated as also the fact that, on patient long-continued washing, the adsorbed electrolyte can be removed almost completely so that no such marked acid reaction develops in contact with potassium chloride solution.

(2) But when the precipitation takes place in presence of alkalis the well-washed precipitate liberates only slightly higher concentration of alkalis in contact with neutral potassium chloride solution, than in contact with water. The maximum alkalinity observed is a p_H value equal to 8 only while the water of the parallel experiment shows a p_H value equal to 7.2. This is to be expected as the alkali metal ions (sodium and potassium hydroxides have been used) are not primarily adsorbed. Only a few mobile hydroxyl ions are probably present having as their partner the outermost layer of barium ions lying on the surface.

(3) At low concentrations the solution of the alkali salts of these acids increase, in the cases so far studied, the negative charge of surface.

(4) The adsorption of acids can be shown analytically (cf. Weiser and others, *loc. cit.*).

(5) The amount of acid liberated in presence of neutral salts is not determined by the weight of barium sulphate used but depends on the conditions under which adsorption has taken place. Thus the experiments when repeated with barium sulphate precipitated from equivalent quantities of barium chloride and potassium sulphate in the absence of acids and subsequently washed carefully with water though showing similar results liberate much smaller amounts of acid with potassium chloride. This fact shows that much greater adsorption takes place during

precipitation and that the ratio of the amount of replaceable hydrogen ions to the mass of the adsorbent varies with the conditions of preparation of the adsorbent.

(6) The ease with which the hydrogen ions are replaced by alkali metal cations (an acid reaction is developed immediately on mixing) and the negative charge show that they exist mostly in the mobile layer.

Experiments have been done with barium sulphate using neutral salts other than potassium chloride and similar results have been observed.

Experiments with other Polar Precipitates

The insoluble salts mentioned below have also been investigated. The precipitation took place in the presence of acids. The liberation of alkalis by neutral salts is very small in those cases where the experiments could be carried out with alkalis instead of acids. The precipitates used were barium chromate, lead sulphate, lead chromate, lead iodate, silver chloride, silver bromide, silver chromate, silver iodide and strontium sulphate.

The lead and silver salts with adsorbed acids do not give an acid extract with potassium chloride but liberate acids in contact with a solution of barium chloride. p_H changes from 6.2 to 5, the p_H of the blank containing water changes from 6.4 to 5.8 showing that barium ions can replace hydrogen ions with greater facility than potassium ions can. The failure to obtain an acid extract with potassium chloride is probably also due to the small amount of the acid that remain adsorbed when the sample is washed carefully.

These experiments leave on doubt as to the existence of the type of reaction formulated by the writer. A much more interesting and in a sense novel result has been obtained in the course of these experiments.

C. Generation of Acids or Alkalis during Precipitation of Barium Sulphate from 'neutral' Salt Solutions.

The writer along with Fajans (Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173, and references to literature given therein) have emphasised the strong adsorption of a constituent ion by a polar precipitate. A precipitate like barium sulphate can be expected to adsorb barium and sulphate ions strongly. It has been found that (1) when precipitated by an excess of potassium sulphate from barium chloride the surface adsorbs sulphate ions. Their presence in the surface can be shown from electro-osmotic or cataphoretic experiments. The precipitate is negatively charged. (2) Similarly when precipitated from excess of barium chloride the surface becomes positively charged.

(3) The adsorption of electrolytes can also be shown analytically. Here, therefore, we get two systems resulting from the adsorption of electrolytes by the same adsorbent one of which is positively charged and the other negatively charged, *i.e.*, the primarily adsorbed ion is a cation in the one case and an anion in the other case.

The two systems may be represented as follows :—

and

Systems III and IV have easily replaceable anions and cations respectively as these ions constitute the mobile layer of ions. On treatment with neutral salts, the anions will be replaced in system III and the cations in system IV. This has been observed to be the case. It must however be stated, as has already been pointed out, that the adsorbed electrolyte comes out in traces on washing

with fresh quantities of water or electrolyte, which is to be expected as there is an equilibrium between the adsorbed quantity and the concentration of the solute in solution and completely irreversible adsorption is a theoretical limiting case.

(4) From our point of view the following reactions are possible :—

and

The actual demonstration of the formation of both acid and alkali with the same adsorbent is rather difficult. The amount of the acid or alkali liberated depends on the total amount of the cation or anion primarily adsorbed and on the relative adsorbabilities of the hydrogen ion and the cation in one case, and of the hydroxyl ion and the anion in the other case. It has to be remembered that the replacement of the cation or the anion by hydrogen or hydroxyl ions respectively also depend on the concentration of the latter ions in pure water which is very small. Moreover, there is always the probability of the adsorbed electrolyte being removed on long continued washing, which has therefore to be avoided.

We have, however, been able to demonstrate the formation of acid and alkali with barium sulphate under the following conditions. If an amount of potassium sulphate be mixed with less than equivalent quantity of barium chloride the medium develops an alkaline reaction up to

$p_H = 11$; on the other hand with excess of barium chloride it develops an acid reaction of $p_H = 5$. The alkalinity and the acidity are also observed with barium nitrate and sulphate of the alkali metals. The conditions appear to be very favourable in this instance for the precipitation takes place in a medium containing the ions which are adsorbed and for the reason that the adsorption of the constituent ion is generally stronger than that of the other ions. Besides the adsorbed electrolytes are not removed as the experiment does not involve any washing.

It has been remarked before that lead and silver salts do not adsorb electrolytes to the same extent as barium sulphate does and this is probably responsible for our failure to obtain similar results with these salts. Our method of procedure precludes the observation of slight changes in the reaction of the medium. Further experiments on these lines are in progress.

D. Adsorption of Water and its Constituent Ions in their Relation to Hydrolytic Adsorption.

It has been stated before that the adsorbent need not be polar in character. We started with the substance BA because of the known capacity of such substances to adsorb electrolytes and in order to show that under certain conditions both acids and alkalis may be expected to be liberated from the interaction between water and the same insoluble salt containing adsorbed electrolytes.

We shall now consider the case where the adsorbent has a strong capacity to 'primarily' adsorb either hydrogen or hydroxyl ions, or both.

(1) *Primary Adsorption of Hydroxyl Ions.*

The system has an acidic character.

We shall assume the system to be such that it can adsorb hydroxyl ions to a much greater extent than it can

adsorb hydrogen ions. Such a substance will have easily replaceable hydrogen ions in the mobile sheet and will act like an acid with the following characteristics, which differentiate it from ordinary acids.

(i) The substance will have a negative charge in contact with water, because of the adsorption of hydroxyl ions.

(ii) The adsorption of hydroxyl ions will evidently depend on their concentration in the solution and more will be adsorbed from an alkaline solution than from water unless the adsorption is so strong that the surface is saturated at the low hydroxyl ion concentration of pure water. The probability of such a state of affairs is remote. The substance will therefore adsorb alkalis in equivalent quantities so long as the activity of the hydroxyl ions is constant and the cation is not primarily adsorbed.

(iii) The negative charge will therefore increase on the addition of alkali from the greater adsorption of hydroxyl ions. Of course, at high concentrations of the alkali, the charge may decrease when the electrical adsorption of the cation predominates.

(iv) *The amount of replaceable hydrogen ions per gram adsorbent* is evidently constant for a given sample of the adsorbent so long as the concentration of hydroxyl ions in the solution correspond to that of neutral water and the solution does not contain acids with adsorbable anions or neutral salts with adsorbable cations, which can displace the primarily adsorbed hydroxyl ions.

In the case where acids only are present in the solution the total amount of anions adsorbed (hydroxyl and other anions) will determine the total amount of replaceable hydrogen ions, *i.e.*, the maximum amount which is theoretically replaceable.

(v) If anions only are adsorbed then for the general case *the total amount of replaceable cations* (including hydrogen

ions), is determined by the total amount of anions (including hydroxyl ions) 'primarily' adsorbed.

(vi) The 'saturation capacity' of the surface with reference to cations (including hydrogen ion and bases) will depend on the amount of anions that can be adsorbed.

If we consider as Langmuir has suggested, that the number of places in the surface, where the anions are adsorbed, are determined by chemical valence, then the maximum amounts of different anions necessary to saturate the surface will follow a simple numerical ratio. The amount actually adsorbed will however depend on the composition of the solution.

The relationships will be simpler when the adsorbent has the strongest affinity for hydroxyl ions so that other anions are primarily adsorbed to a very small extent. It is also assumed that cation are not primarily adsorbed. The maximum amount of replaceable hydrogen ions is determined by the amount of hydroxyl ions adsorbed which is a constant quantity so long as the activity of the hydroxyl ions in the solution remains constant and the adsorption of the other anions does not change their number. The stoichiometric ratio of the amount of replaceable hydrogen ions to the number of gram molecules of the adsorbent, will depend on the specific surface and the capacity of the adsorbent to adsorb per unit surface.

(vii) On the addition of an acid the negative charge will decrease and there will be no reversal of charge unless there is also a "fixed" layer of primarily adsorbed molecules of water, provided that the surface cannot primarily adsorb hydrogen ions.

(viii) The adsorption of cations from salt solutions will not be equivalent to that of anions (excepting the case of alkalis) as there is always a replacement of the hydrogen ions by the cations.

In other respects the system will behave like the system BA with adsorbed acids.

(2) *Primary Adsorption of Hydrogen Ions.*

The system has a basic character.

The parallel case of a strong primary adsorption of hydrogen ions needs no further discussion. We might just mention that the surface will be charged positively in contact with water, will liberate alkalis in contact with 'neutral' salt solutions. The adsorption of the anion will be greater than that of the cation, the positive charge will increase in presence of acids and will diminish in contact with alkalis.

(3) *Primary Adsorption of Water Molecules.*

The system has an amphoteric character.

In the introductory portion of this paper it has been pointed out that hydrolytic adsorption can only result from a displacement (direct or indirect as shown below) of adsorbed hydrogen or hydroxyl ions by a cation or an anion respectively. In the preceding pages it has been stated that these displaced hydrogen ions or hydroxyl ions can come either from adsorbed acids or alkalis respectively or from the constituent ions of water. *We have so far associated the case of replacement of hydrogen or hydroxyl ions by 'neutral' salt solutions with their presence in the sheet of mobile ions of the double layer as electro-osmotic or allied measurements.* This view assumes that the surface carries an electric charge opposite in sign to that of the replaceable ion (hydrogen or hydroxyl) due to the primary adsorption of ions of one kind in excess. For the sake of simplicity we have so long considered that ions of one sign only are primarily adsorbed.

A theoretically important case which has not been considered so far is the rôle of the layer of primarily adsorbed molecules of water. From the point of view suggested in this and previous papers a 'primarily' adsorbed layer will act as a 'solid' layer (*cf. Phil. Mag., loc. cit., 332*). It was suggested that such a system has in a sense amphoteric properties as the surface can neutralise or combine with hydrogen and hydroxyl ions in solution. The surface may acquire a positive charge in acid solutions and a negative charge in alkaline solutions. The conditions for such behaviour have been discussed in detail in the paper referred to above. These properties have been attributed to the dissociations of the 'primarily' adsorbed (solid layer) molecules of water. The case where the surface adsorbs primarily hydroxyl ions in addition to water molecules has also been discussed. *In general, however, such a surface will have a primarily adsorbed layer of neutral molecules of water, hydrogen and hydroxyl ions in equal number formed by the dissociation of small number of these molecules, and it may have in addition an excess of either hydrogen or hydroxyl ions, as the result of primary adsorption.* Their relative numbers will depend on the nature of the substance. *The system will have an acidic character when an excess of hydroxyl ions is primarily adsorbed and in suitable cases the number of hydrogen ions may be quite small compared to that of hydroxyl ions. Similarly a system will have a 'basic' character when an excess of hydrogen ions is primarily adsorbed and a markedly amphoteric character when they are present in sufficient but equal amounts.* Electro-osmotic and allied experiments give an idea of the net excess in charge and throw no light on the amount of each ion present in the primarily adsorbed layer.

The question now arises "Are these ions in the 'solid,' *i.e.*, the primarily adsorbed layer displaceable by

other ions?" *A priori* there is no reason why they will not be so replaceable. Such a replacement is however distinct from exchange of ions of *the same sign* between those present in the mobile sheet of the double layer and those in the solution. Such exchanges are wholly electrical in nature and has very little to do with the chemical nature of the cations. The mobility, the charge and the adsorbability as defined in a previous paper (*Far. Soc. Disc., The Physics and Chemistry of Colloids, loc. cit., p. 105*) determine the capacity of the cations in the solution to replace those in the mobile sheet.

When the displacing ion is a cation the following possibilities arise :—(1) The cation can displace the hydrogen or hydroxyl ions ; or, (2) can take the place of neutral molecule of water ; or, (3) be adsorbed independently and directly without displacement. One or more of these possibilities may also occur simultaneously.

Displacement of Hydroxyl Ions from the Primary Layer.

(a) A replacement of a hydroxyl ion by a primarily adsorbed anion will not alter the charge of the surface unless there is a simultaneous independent adsorption of the anion. It will result in hydrolysis and alkali will be liberated and the acid will remain in the surface.

(b) A mere replacement of the hydroxyl ion by a 'primarily' adsorbed cation will not result in hydrolysis, for, to ensure the electrical neutrality of the double layer as a whole, the displaced hydroxyl ions must remain in the mobile sheet. If however the anion of the salt is present in sufficient concentration it may displace the hydroxyl ions from the mobile sheet, and alkali will be liberated. The surface will show a marked increase in the positive charge. One univalent cation so adsorbed will augment the positive electrical charge of the surface by two units due to the simultaneous displacement of the hydroxyl ions. On

the other hand if the surface had initially an excess of hydroxyl ions adsorbed (*i.e.*, if it has a marked negative charge in contact with pure water), the liberated hydroxyl ions will combine with hydrogen ions in the mobile sheet to restore the equilibrium between the two ions in these regions. Alkalis can only be liberated when the displaced hydroxyl ions are greater in amount than the hydrogen ions in the second sheet.

Displacement of Hydrogen Ions from the Primary Layer.

Parallel conclusions are to be drawn regarding the displacement of hydrogen or hydroxyl ions by anions.

Electrical Neutralisation of the Hydrogen or Hydroxyl Ions in the Primary Layer.

Another type of reaction that is theoretically possible from our point of view is that between the hydrogen and hydroxyl ions formed from the dissociation of water molecules in the primarily adsorbed layer and the oppositely charged ions in the solution. The power of the hydrogen or hydroxyl ions to impart a positive or negative charge respectively to a surface, has been explained on the basis of interaction between hydrogen or hydroxyl ions in the surface and hydroxyl and hydrogen ions respectively in the solution. In this case the electrical neutralisation of opposite charges coincide also with the formation of undissociated molecules of water. One might also imagine a neutralisation of the electrical charges of the hydrogen or hydroxyl ions on the surface (resulting from the dissociation of the fixed layer of water molecules) and an oppositely charged ion in solution. The process is essentially a type of "electrical adsorption." This type of interaction would lead to different conclusions from the foregoing. *No alkalis can be liberated by the interaction between the surface and a cation and no acids can be*

liberated by interaction between the surface and an anion as oppositely charged ions are held together in the surface. The liberation of hydrogen ions by cations is only possible if we further assume that the force restraining the partner hydrogen ion of the neutralised hydroxyl ion is electrical in nature and as soon as the cation neutralises the charge of the hydroxyl ions the hydrogen ions become free to move out into the solution. The change in electrical charge will be slight or nil. Similarly an anion can only liberate alkalis.

In the foregoing we have pointed out several theoretically possible types of interaction between adsorbed water molecules, its constituent ions and ions in the solution, which can result in the liberation of acids or alkalis. We have also shown that a simultaneous measurement of the electrical condition of the surface, a study of the case with which different cations and anions liberate acids or alkalis, as also a study as to whether suitable cations or anions can liberate both alkalis and acids are necessary before we can form a definite picture of the nature of the interaction between the ions in the surface and those in the solution. Investigations from this point of view have not been attempted previously and hence in the few instances where experiments on hydrolytic adsorption have been carried out, it is difficult to draw a definite conclusion as to the type of the interaction. However, during the last few years a number of interesting investigations have been carried out which serve to illustrate our point of view.

(4) Hydrated Silica as a Substance which has a strong Capacity to Adsorb Hydroxyl Ions and to a less extent other Anions.

The nature of the interaction between silica and neutral salts is of considerable interest in agricultural

chemistry and has been the subject of controversy (Joseph and Hancock, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2022).

We shall briefly state here the experimental evidence that has been obtained in collaboration with Messrs. Kamala Charan Bhattacharya, Bhivas Chandra Ghosh and K. Krishna Murti. As the purity of the samples we have used has been questioned (Joseph and Hancock, *loc. cit.*) it is desirable to state that we have used hydrated silica obtained from the hydrolysis of doubly distilled silicon tetrachloride in vessels of fused transparent silica. Transparent silica vessels have been used as a rule. The hydrated silica contains traces of chlorine and excluding water contain 99.99% of silicon dioxide. The water content varied from about 90% to 50% of the total weight of the substance.

(1) Hydrated silica has a marked negative charge in contact with pure water, no matter how long the substance is washed with water.

(2) On the addition of acids (HCl, HNO₃) the negative charge decreases (*cf. Nature*, December 2, 1924). No reversal of the charge has been observed (*cf. Phil. Mag.*, *loc. cit.*, 330).

(3) In contact with solutions of neutral salts (NaCl, KCl, BaCl₂, RbNO₃, KNO₃, LiCl, LiNO₃) at low concentrations there is an increase in the negative charge, which, as is to be expected, is most marked in the case of lithium chloride, and the order of the cations arranged according to their power to decrease the negative charge is as follows: —H > Ba > Rb > K > Na > Li. The salts of hydrogen and barium mentioned above show no increase in negative charge. Using equivalent concentration of potassium salts it was found that the negative charge of the surface is increased by anions in the following order: oxalate > sulphate > chloride > bromide > nitrate.

The increase in the negative charge shows definitely the 'primary' adsorption of these anions.

(4) Even in contact with very dilute solutions of alkalis the negative charge increased markedly and the increase is much greater than in the case of other salts of the same alkali metal cation (similar observations have also been made by others).

(5) Fourteen gms. of hydrated silica containing 11.2 gms. of water and 2.8 grams of silicon dioxide were kept in contact with 100 c.c. of saturated solution of potassium chloride for twenty-four hours. As much of the salt solution was decanted off, as could be separated without removing any silica and the volume and p_H of the extract was determined. A fresh volume of saturated potassium chloride was then added and after a contact of twenty-four hours or so the p_H and the volume of the decanted liquid were again determined. This process was repeated till the p_H of the extract became equivalent to that of the potassium chloride solution used. *In this manner it is possible to determine the total amount of replaceable hydrogen ions.* The hydrated silica contain 13.3 gram mols. of water per gram molecule of silicon dioxide and of these 13.3 gram mols. of water 3.5×10^{-4} gram atom of hydrogen ions is replaceable by potassium.

It will be seen that there is no simple stoichiometric relation between the amount of replaceable hydrogen ions and the number of gm. mols. of SiO_2 .

(6) If the reaction is really to be represented as follows :

or

(cf. Mellor, *Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, London, 1913, p. 172, also Joseph, *loc. cit.*) one would expect that so long as the two solid phases P and Q co-exist the equilibrium concentration of the hydrogen ions would be determined by the concentration of potassium chloride used and would be constant when the latter remains constant. It is found, however, that as the washing continues the acidity of the extract falls steadily. It might be argued that equilibrium has not been attained and that as more of the insoluble acid P is transformed into the insoluble salt Q, it requires a much larger time to attain the equilibrium concentration. But this is not so, because if the time of contact is increased and the contents are shaken at intervals a maximum acidity is obtained which does not change any further with time.

(7) The increase in the negative charge showing the primary adsorption of anions leads us to expect the adsorption of acids (and salts). Ten grams of carefully washed hydrated silica are transferred to a Gooch crucible made of transparent fused silica without any asbestos or porcelain parts. If now 10 c.c. of an acid solution (HCl) of $p_H=3.4$ are filtered through it the p_H of the extract rises to 4.6 showing that as much as 90% of the acid has been adsorbed. Other experiments have shown a change in p_H as large as from 3.2 to 5.0. Blank experiments using water instead of acid show no change in p_H . Also if no hydrated silica be present there is no change in p_H of the acid showing that the change in p_H is not due to any spurious effect. Further the extracted acid does not show the presence of ammonia. Neither can the water present in silica account for the diminution in concentration.

The amount of acid taken up is equal to 2.7×10^{-4} gram atoms of hydrogen ions per gm. mole of silicon dioxide.

(8) That silica can adsorb acids can also be shown directly in the following manner. Ten gms. of hydrated silica is shaken with 5 c. c. of normal oxalic acid and left in contact for a few hours. The silica is then washed with pure water till the water obtained after twelve hours' contact fails to decolourise 3 drops of an acid solution of $N/100$ permanganate when heated to about 60° for a quarter of an hour. The silica, however, decolourised 1.4 c. c. or about 40 drops of $N/100$ permanganate solution. This observation has been repeatedly confirmed.

The amount thus adsorbed works out to be 4.2×10^{-4} gram atoms of hydrogen per gm. molecule of SiO_2 .

It will be seen that the amounts given under (5), (7) and (8), ($3 \times 5 \times 10$, 2.7×10^{-4} , 4.2×10^{-4} gram atoms of hydrogen ions respectively per gram mol. of silicon dioxide) are comparable quantities. These quantities also illustrate the smallness of the amounts primarily adsorbed.

(5) *Experiments with Hydrated Manganese Dioxide.*

Hydrated silica is not the only substance which behaves in the above manner. Hydrated manganese dioxide prepared by Volhard's method has similar characteristics. As full experimental details and discussions will be published in a separate paper, we shall briefly relate an aspect of the experimental results which will illustrate the advantage of our point of view over the usual chemical one. It has already been stated that if the chemical point of view be correct there ought to be a simple relation between the concentration (or activity) of the cation of the neutral salt and that of the hydrogen ions in the solution. We have found that this is not the case either with hydrated silica or with hydrated manganese dioxide. The concentration of the liberated hydrogen ions rises much more

slowly than that of the salt and reaches a maximum value.* If we compare the influence of different cations, we find from the following table that at low concentrations the p_H of the liberated hydrogen ions increases in the following order: $Ba > K > Na > Li$. *From the chemical point of view in the presence of the two insoluble phases P and Q the higher concentration (or activity) of the hydrogen ions is to be referred to the smaller solubility of the corresponding salt Q and the solubility must be assumed to increase in the order: $Ba < K < Na < Li$* As pointed out in a previous paper this order is met with in a large number of cases and for substances which are of widely different chemical composition (*vide Phil. Mag., loc. cit., pp. 339, 340, 343*), and it is rather unusual that the solubilities will always be related in the above manner. The data shows moreover, that as the concentration of the cation rises the equilibrium hydrogen ion concentration rapidly tends to a constant value which is nearly the same for all the alkali metal cations. Besides the chemical point of view does not account for the electro-osmotic data. On the other hand the point of view advanced here gives a consistent explanation of these facts and in fact can predict a number of relationships.

The amount of liberated acid depends on the capacity of the cation to displace the hydrogen ions from the double layer. The concentration of the latter depends on the ratio of the two ions, hydrogen and the cation in the double layer and is determined by the electrical adsorbability of the cations. The electrical adsorbability of the cation also determines its effect on the negative

* The maximum hydrogen ion concentration does not represent the liberation of the total amount of replaceable hydrogen ions as fresh quantities of acid are set free on adding a fresh quantity of the salt solution to the solid residue. The maximum acid concentration, therefore, cannot represent a complete conversion of P into Q.

charge of the surface and therefore the same order ought to be observed in both cases. This fact is brought out in Table I.

TABLE I.*

Concentration of electrolytes.	Rate of Electro-osmotic Flow.				Concentrations.	pH Values.			
	KCl	NaCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂		KCl	NaCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂
O	9.8	9.8	9.8	9.8	N	2.16	2.15	2.17	...
N/5000	5.4	N/5	2.28	2.27
N/3000	7.4	16	17.7	...	N/10	2.34	2.47	2.57	2.09
N/1000	5.4	16.3	16.6	+8.0	N/100	2.99	2.76	3.00	2.21
N/500	3.8	18.1	14.3	+13.0	N/200	2.40
N/250	3.0	11.7	13.4	+16.7	O	5.8	5.8	5.8	5.8
N/125	+14.5					

The fact that at higher cation concentrations the hydrogen ion concentration tends to a limiting value can also be accounted for. The adsorbability of the cation, the variation in the electrical charge of the surface with its concentration, and the amount and concentration of liberated hydrogen ions are closely related to one another. The total amount of replaceable hydrogen ions, the composition of the primarily adsorbed layer and of the mobile layer of ions are to be taken into consideration, in order to elucidate the relationships between the electrical charge

* The electro-osmotic data given above represents the distance moved by the air bubble in 3 minutes. With BaCl₂ reversal of charge was obtained at N/1000 for the sample which has used in the electro-osmotic experiments. This sample was much coarser grained and more thoroughly washed than the one used for measurement of p_H . The sample of MnO₂ used for p_H measurement showed a reversal of charge with BaCl₂ between N/200 and N/66.6. The p_H of water kept in contact with MnO₂ for 24 hrs. is 5.8. E. M. F. measurements have been made in each case to check the values obtained from the use of indicators. The two are in satisfactory agreement.

and the concentrations of liberated hydrogen ions. These relationships have sufficiently brought out the unsuitability of the usual chemical point of view. As it will be necessary to enter too much into detail the consideration of these interesting relationships will be taken up in the paper dealing with hydrated manganese dioxide.

(6) *Experiments of Bartell and Miller on Active Charcoal.*

Bartell and Miller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1866 ; *ibid.*, 1923, 45, 1106 ; 1924, 46, 1150 ; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 992), have clearly demonstrated hydrolytic adsorption by ash-free active charcoal from sugar. Their experiments also prove the existence of the type of reactions postulated under D. The ease with which simple electrolytes like solutions of potassium chloride or potassium nitrate can liberate alkalis leads one to expect that hydroxyl ions are present in the mobile sheet of the double layer. There are, however, no measurements of the electrical charge and of the total amount of replaceable alkali and in the absence of these data, it is not possible to give a definite account of the changes taking place in the surface layer. Such measurements are more necessary because Bartell and Miller have used not only simple electrolytes like potassium chloride but have also used electrolytes containing complex cations and anions and chemical affinity between the surface atoms and the ions in the solution will have to be considered. The correlation of the electrical with the chemical data is of great interest. The data of Bartell and Miller, though incomplete in the above sense, points strongly to the capacity of their charcoal to adsorb preferentially hydrogen ions and that the surface has probably a weak or very little power to adsorb hydroxyl ions. The ease with which alkalis are liberated (in fact all ordinary salts excepting that of

mercury and silver liberate alkalis only) and the fact that alkalis are not at all adsorbed support this statement (*vide* Miller, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 45, *loc. cit.*). The liberation of acids by silver and mercury salts are in agreement with the strong primary adsorption of these ions as shown by their capacity to impart a positive charge to the surface (*cf.* Mukherjee and Roy, *loc. cit.*). Their charcoal would probably show a positive charge in contact with pure water and would show only a small, if at all any, negative charge in the presence of alkalis. Acids are likely to increase the positive charge, a detailed consideration of the nature of the changes in the surface layer must be postponed till the necessary data have been obtained.

In the foregoing we have outlined some simpler types of reactions to illustrate our theory. More complicated cases will be considered in the papers to follow.

We have so far considered reactions concerning the primarily adsorbed layer and ions in the mobile sheet of the double layer. We shall now consider more fully the rôle of the 'adsorbed' water in the analytical estimation of the amount of 'primary' adsorption and in the retention of a solute by an adsorbent as these questions have a very important bearing on subsequent papers.

E. *Hydration of the Substance and its Relation to Adsorption.*

The primarily adsorbed layer is probably one molecule thick and does not extend much beyond it. The molecules in this layer are held by chemical affinity of the atoms on the surface of the adsorbent and act as a 'solid' layer. Ions in the mobile layer are also not wholly free to move in the sense that there must be always an amount of ions equivalent to the free and fixed charge on the surface.

There is, however, evidence to show that the 'adsorbed' layer of molecules of water, which hydrate the surface,

is not a unimolecular layer but rather forms a layer several molecules in depth. Thus hydrated silica containing as much as 80% of water behaves to most purposes as a solid. The number of gm. molecules of water per gram molecule of silicon dioxide works out at about 13 mols of water to 1 mol of silicon dioxide. It is evident that the hydration layer must be several molecules deep.

The strength with which the successive layers of water molecules are held in the poly-molecular hydration layer will fall off rapidly, as the distance from the adsorbing surface increases. A '*fully hydrated surface*' can be defined as one where the poly-molecular layer is sufficiently deep so that the outermost layer of water molecules will show the same vapour pressure as pure water at that temperature. As the successive layer of water molecules *counting from the outermost layer evaporates*, the vapour pressure will diminish because the successive layer of molecules are adsorbed with increasing intensity. It is well known that the presence of water vapour falls off rapidly with the percentage of hydration. The layer immediately in contact with the surface is held by chemical affinity and there is a marked drop in the intensity of the forces with which the following layers are held by the surface. Thus we would distinguish between the 'primarily' adsorbed layer and the poly-molecular hydration layer. Different types of forces, as distinct from what we ordinarily refer to as chemical valence and analogous to inter-molecular attraction as represented by the a/v^2 term in van der Waals's equation, or forces akin to those causing the hydration of ions are probably responsible for the formation of this layer. The water molecules whose dissociation has been discussed are assumed to be in the 'primarily' adsorbed layer.

*Adsorption of Water and Analytical Estimation
of Adsorption.*

The importance of the adsorption of water in analytical estimation of adsorption has been emphasised by Bancroft and Williams and more recently by Ostwald and Izagguire (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1919, 30, 279). Bancroft pointed out that the water-content of the adsorbent is to be taken into consideration in calculating the amount adsorbed (*cf.* Weiser and Sherrick, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1919, 23, 205). The effect of adsorbed water is considered to be merely to dilute the solution in virtue of the penetration of the solute molecules into the 'hydration' layer. Apparently the assumption is being made that the distribution coefficients of the solute between the solution and the adsorbed layer of water is unity. The hydration layer does not behave exactly as a 'solid' layer as salts are not soluble in ice; that is, in the hydration layer probably there is no regular lattice arrangement as in solid ice.

On the other hand it is not possible to look upon the effect as mere dilution with water. There is always a time factor involved in the diffusion of the solute from the 'hydration' layer into the bulk of the liquid and from experiments on the time necessary to wash out the solute it appears to us that a simple mechanical mixing of the water in the hydration layer with the solution during washing, cannot account for the time taken to remove the solute from the hydration layer. Very accurate measurements of the change in concentration of a solution in contact with a hydrated adsorbent will enable us to determine the relationship between the concentration in the hydration layer and that in the bulk of the solution. We have already stated that small but demonstrable quantities of acids are adsorbed by hydrated silica and hydrated manganese dioxide. The partition ratio cannot therefore

be unity though we have found at higher concentrations the small amount actually adsorbed does not materially alter the total concentration and a partition coefficient equal to unity is observed. Moreover, the internal pressure of the water in the hydration layer is certainly different from that inside the pure liquid, and it is to be expected, that this would change the free energy and the partition coefficient would be different from unity though the magnitude of the effect as we have seen is probably very small. The well-known suggestion of Lagergren (*loc. cit.*) and also the considerations put forth by Williams (*cf. Phil. Mag., loc. cit.*, pp. 323-24) also lead us to expect a difference in concentration and an adsorption effect from the existence of the hydration layer and more exact and detailed experiments are desirable.

We have entered into a detailed consideration of the effect of the water of hydration with a view to show that the estimation of the amount of primary adsorption by direct analytical measurements is beset with considerable difficulties and to show that the effect of the water of hydration is not simply one of dilution. We are of opinion that the adsorbed amount should be defined as the total amount taken up by the adsorbent including that by the water of hydration. This method of representation is more advantageous as emphasising the fact that a solid can take up a solute which is not soluble in it, in virtue of its water of hydration. Attention is not directed to this fact if the results are expressed in the usual way. Ostwald and Izagguire (*loc. cit.*) state 'Es werden nicht "gelöste Stoffe," es werden vielmehr "Lösungen" selbst adsorbiert. Es ist demnach auch sprechlich, schärfer nicht von Adsorptionen, "in" oder "aus" Lösungen sondern von Adsorptionen "von" Lösungen zu sprechen.'

The retention of electrolytes (including acids) in the hydration layer is of considerable importance in

agricultural chemistry. There is always a time factor depending on the rate of diffusion from the surface layers which makes the removal of the solute by drainage water slow and difficult. Also the difference between adsorption as usually determined by analysis and the adsorption we are considering just now, is none of degree so far as the rate of removal by washing is concerned. In the case of the 'primarily' adsorbed molecules all are not free to diffuse but in the latter case the freedom of the solute molecules to diffuse out of the hydration layer is almost equal to that of the molecule in the bulk of the liquid. On the other hand the total amount of solute in the hydration layer is much greater. So that in considering the retention of the solute, say, by soil particles, the effect of the hydration is not less important than that represented by the amount adsorbed after correcting for the hydration. The writer therefore suggests that the adsorption ought to be calculated in terms of the total change in concentration of the solution brought in contact with the solid adsorbent—irrespective of the water content of the latter, and that the facts can be better represented by simultaneously mentioning the 'hydration' of the solid phase.

(F) *Base-Exchange in Soils.*

The application of the considerations set forth above to the problem of exchange of bases in soil is evident, in so far as the exchange is to be attributed to an interaction between the ions in the solution with those in the double layer. The same considerations regarding the 'saturation capacity' of the surface with respect to different anions, the electrical and chemical adsorbability of various cations and the concentrations of the different ions in the solutions are applicable to this case. It is our

intention to deal with the exchange of bases in soils from our point of view in one of the papers of this series.

Conclusion and Summary.

In conclusion we would like to emphasize that we have only considered certain simple theoretically possible cases and that more complicated changes where chemical affinity plays a very important part and which are to be met with quietly frequently, have been left out of consideration.

In this paper, the view advanced by the author regarding the distribution of ions in the 'Helmholtz' electrical double layer have been further developed to account for hydrolytic adsorption. The different types of reaction, which from this point of view can liberate acids or alkalis from neutral salt solutions, have been described and a brief summary of the experimental results to be communicated in the following papers, has been given in support.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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